

Software evaluation results

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Presentation plan

- Brief overview of user requirements
- Repository software and specifications
- Software overview
- User requirements test results
- Administrative requirements test results

Brief requirements overview

- Preserve research data and metadata in a FAIR way
- Be able to share publications and research results within the framework of the central repository, differentiate access rights
- Have tools for analysing, visualizing and previewing data and metadata
- Enable operations with metadata through SPARQL
- Provide API for easy access and data management

Repository Software

Software for repositories

- InvenioRDM

Version: 9.1

Architecture:

Load balancers: HAProxy, Nginx or others.

Web servers: Nginx, Apache or others.

Application servers: UWSGI, Gunicorn or mod_wsgi.

Distributed task queue: Celery

Database: PostgreSQL, MySQL or SQLite.

Search engine: Elasticsearch (v6 and v7).

Message queue: RabbitMQ, Redis or Amazon SQS.

Cache system: Redis or Memcache.

Storage system: Local, S3, XRootD, WebDAV and more.

Dataverse

Version: 5.12.1

Architecture:

Load balancers: HAProxy, Nginx or others.

Web servers: Nginx, Apache or others.

Application servers: Payara.

Database: PostgreSQL

Search engine: Apache Solr (v8).

Cache system: Redis or Memcache.

Storage system: Local, S3.

Each of these products were installed on virtual machines in bwCloud (<https://www.bw-cloud.org/>). This cloud-based "infrastructure as a service" environment is specifically designed for research and teaching in Baden-Württemberg.

Software for repositories

- DSpace

Version: 7

Architecture:

Load balancers: HAProxy, Nginx or others.

Web servers: Tomcat, Jetty.

Application servers: Tomcat, nodejs.

Database: PostgreSQL, Oracle.

Search engine: Apache Solr.

Message queue: RabbitMQ, Redis or Amazon SQS.

Cache system: Redis or Memcache.

Storage system: Local, S3.

CKAN

Version: 2.9.7

Architecture:

Load balancers: HAProxy, Nginx or others.

Web servers: Nginx, Apache, Tomcat.

Application servers: UWSGI, Gunicorn or mod_wsgi.

Database: PostgreSQL, MySQL or SQLite.

Search engine: Solr.

Message queue: RabbitMQ, Redis or Amazon SQS.

Cache system: Redis or Memcache.

Storage system: Local, S3, XRootD, WebDAV and more.

InvenioRDM overview

- Communities (similar as folder)
- Inside of each community - related uploads (as data sets)

InvenioRDM overview (continue)

The screenshot shows the InvenioRDM record creation interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below this, a prompt asks to 'Select the community where you want to submit your record.' The main area is divided into two columns. The left column contains the 'Files' section with a 'Drag and drop files' area and an 'Upload files' button. Below this is the 'Basic information' section, which includes a 'Resource type' dropdown, a 'Title' field with an 'Add titles' button, and a 'Publication date' field with the value '2023-03-16'. A note at the bottom of this section reads: 'In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE. e.g. 1939/1945.' The right column contains a 'Draft' section with 'Save draft', 'Preview', and 'Publish' buttons. Below this is the 'Visibility' section, which has 'Full record' and 'Files only' options, both set to 'Public'. A green box indicates 'Public: The record and files are publicly accessible.' At the bottom of the right column is an 'Options' section with an 'Apply an embargo' button and a note: 'Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.'

- Metadata required and non-required fields during upload

The screenshot shows the 'Recommended information' section of the InvenioRDM record creation interface. It includes a 'Creators' section with an 'Add creator' button. The 'Description' section features a rich text editor with a 'Paragraph' dropdown and various formatting options (bold, italic, link, list, indent, quote, undo, redo). Below the description is an 'Add description' button. The 'Licenses' section shows 'Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International' as the selected license, with a brief description and 'Edit' and 'Remove' buttons. There are also 'Add standard' and 'Add custom' buttons. The 'Recommended information' section is expanded to show 'Contributors' (with an 'Add contributor' button), 'Subjects' (with a 'Suggest from' dropdown set to 'All' and a search field), and 'Languages' (with a search field). At the bottom, there is a 'Dates' section with a table for adding dates:

Date*	Type*	Description
YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD		

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

InvenioRDM overview (continue)

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

invenio-9.1

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

Funding

Awards

+ Add award + Add custom

Alternate identifiers

Alternate identifiers

Identifier * Scheme *

+ Add identifier

Related works

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation * Identifier * Scheme * Resource type

INVENIO RDM Search records... Communities My dashboard

test-community-public Change X Remove

Files

Metadata-only record Storage available 2 out of 100 files 9 bytes out of 10.00 GB

Preview	Filename	Size	Progress
<input type="checkbox"/>	test.txt md5:040f8b0a4021e373c0a4e432827e4f8	4 bytes	100%
<input type="checkbox"/>	test2.txt md5:a60234230209d03319bba1107a472b	5 bytes	100%

Drag and drop files - or - Upload files

File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload.

Basic information

Resource type * Dataset

In review View request

Save draft Preview Submitted for review

Visibility

Full record Public Restricted

The full record is restricted.

Restricted
The record can only be accessed by users specified in the permissions.

Options

Apply an embargo Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Delete

It is possible to create restricted communities. All items will be also restricted.

In public community publications can be restricted or public.

If public and restricted files are planned, separate communities are needed.

Dataverse overview

Welcome to NFDI4Cat repository prototype!

NFDI4Cat collections

Metrics 7 Downloads Contact Share

Samples test-dataverse

Search this dataverse... Advanced Search

Dataverses (5)
Datasets (11)
Files (19)

Dataverse Category
Laboratory (2)
Department (1)
Research Project (1)

Metadata Source
NFDI4Cat collections (11)
SDC4Lit collections (5)

Publication Year
2023 (2)
2022 (4)
2021 (5)

Publication Status
Published (11)
Unpublished (5)
Draft (4)

Author Name
Admin, Dataverse (6)
Dikova, Yulia (5)

Subject
Agricultural Sciences (7)
Engineering (7)
Computer and Information Science (3)
Other (2)
Mathematical Sciences (1)

Deposit Date
2023 (2)
2022 (5)
2021 (4)

1 to 10 of 16 Results

- script_test [Draft] [Unpublished]
Jan 30, 2023 - Dataverse_YL
Dikova, Yulia. 2023. "script_test", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1035>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION
bash script
- test_track_changes_published
Jan 24, 2023 - test-dataverse
Admin, Dataverse. 2023. "test_track_changes_published", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1034>, NFDI4Cat collections, V3
test track changes
- Samples (Dataverse.org)
Jan 17, 2023
- Picture_test
Dec 12, 2022 - test-dataverse-subdataverse
Dikova, Yulia. 2022. "Picture_test", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1029>, NFDI4Cat collections, V1
Pictures
- test-dataverse-subdataverse (Dataverse.org)
Dec 12, 2022 - test-dataverse
- Doc_test [Draft] [Unpublished]
Dec 12, 2022 - test-dataverse-subdataverse
Dikova, Yulia. 2022. "Doc_test", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1028>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION
List of RDF Databases
- Pdf_test [Draft] [Unpublished]
Dec 12, 2022 - Dataverse_YL
Dikova, Yulia. 2022. "Pdf_test", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1027>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION

Welcome to NFDI4Cat repository prototype!

Dataverse_YL [Unpublished]

NFDI4Cat collections > test-dataverse > test-dataverse-subdataverse >

Contact Share Publish Edit

Search this dataverse... Advanced Search + Add Data

New Dataverse New Dataset

Dataverses (1)
Datasets (3)
Files (7)

Dataverse Category
Research Project (1)

Publication Status
Unpublished (4)
Draft (3)

Author Name
Dikova, Yulia (3)

Subject
Engineering (3)

Deposit Date
2023 (1)
2022 (2)

1 to 4 of 4 Results

- script_test [Draft] [Unpublished]
Jan 30, 2023
Dikova, Yulia. 2023. "script_test", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1035>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION
bash script
- Pdf_test [Draft] [Unpublished]
Dec 12, 2022
Dikova, Yulia. 2022. "Pdf_test", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1027>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION
A comparison of research data management platforms Architecture, flexible metadata and interoperability
- New_Test1 [Draft] [Unpublished]
Dec 7, 2022
Dikova, Yulia. 2022. "New_Test1", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1026>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION, UNF:6:CZxAh3RGHEIXJqM2z0d0Og== [fileUNF]
First test dataset for Dataverse
- Dataverse_YL [Unpublished]
Dec 7, 2022 - test-dataverse-subdataverse

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Dataverse - like folder

Dataverse can consist of several dataverses

Dataset - data

Dataverse overview (continue)

The screenshot shows the 'Citation Metadata' section of the Dataverse overview form. It includes fields for Title, Author (Name, Affiliation, Identifier Type), Point of Contact (Name, Affiliation, E-mail), Description (Text, Date), Subject, Keyword (Term, Controlled Vocabulary Name, URL), Related Publication (Citation, Identifier Type, Identifier, URL), and Notes.

The screenshot shows the 'Structural Metadata MODS' and 'Structural Metadata PREMIS' sections. The MODS section includes fields for Deposit Date, Related Item (Related Item Type, TitleInfo Authority URI, Name Authority URI, Name Type), TitleInfo Type, TitleInfo Value URI, TitleInfo Title, Name Value URI, and Name NamePart. The PREMIS section includes fields for Relationship (Relationship Type, Relationship Sub Type, Related Object Identifier Type, Related Object Identifier Value, Related Object Sequence), Object Category, Significant Properties (Significant Properties Type, Significant Properties Value), and Environment (Environment Characteristic, Environment Purpose, Environment Note, Software Name, Software Version, Software Type, Software Other Information, Software Dependency, Hardware Name, Hardware Type, Hardware Other Information).

- More detailed description of the datasets
- Different metadata blocks (here - 3)
- It is possible to create own metadata fields and define metadata set when creating a new dataverse

Dataverse overview (continue)

Welcome to NFDI4@t repository prototype!

Dataverse_YL
Unpublished

NFDI4@t collections > test-dataverse > test-dataverse-subdataverse > Dataverse_YL >

Success! – This dataset has been created.

Info – This draft version needs to be published. When ready for sharing, please publish it so that others can see these changes.

test1
Draft Unpublished

Dikova, Yulia, 2023. "test1", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1036>, NFDI4@t collections, DRAFT VERSION

Cite Dataset + Learn about Data Citation Standards.

Description text
Subject Chemistry
License/Data Use Agreement CC0 1.0

Files Metadata Terms Versions

+ Upload Files

1 File

t1.pdf
Adobe PDF - 172.9 KB
Deposited Mar 17, 2023
MD5: e03..411

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- Access Dataset +
- Publish Dataset +
- Edit Dataset +
- Contact Owner
- Files (Upload)
- Dataset Metrics
- Metadatas
- Terms
- Permissions
- Private URL
- Thumbnails + Widgets
- Delete Dataset

Welcome to NFDI4@t repository prototype!

Dataverse_YL
Unpublished

NFDI4@t collections > test-dataverse > test-dataverse-subdataverse > Dataverse_YL > test1 >

Info – This draft version needs to be published. When ready for sharing, please go to the dataset page to publish it so that others can see these changes.

t1.pdf
This file is part of "test1".
Draft Unpublished

File Citation
Dikova, Yulia, 2023, "test1", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1036>, NFDI4@t collections, DRAFT VERSION: t1.pdf [fileName]

Cite Data File + Learn about Data Citation Standards.

Dataset Citation
Dikova, Yulia, 2023, "test1", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1036>, NFDI4@t collections, DRAFT VERSION

Cite Dataset + Learn about Data Citation Standards.

Preview Metadata Versions

Open in New Window

Received date / Accepted date

Abstract Research data management is rapidly becoming a regular concern for researchers, and institutions need to provide them with platforms to support data organization and preparation for publication. Some institutions have adopted institutional repositories as the basis for data deposit, whereas others are experimenting with richer environments for data description, in spite of the diversity of existing workflows. This paper is a synthetic overview of current platforms that can be used for data management purposes. Adopting a pragmatic view on data management, the paper focuses on solutions that can be adopted in the long-tail of science, where investments in tools and manpower are modest. First, a broad set of data management platforms is presented—some designed for institutional repositories and digital libraries—to select a short list of the more promising ones for data management. These platforms are compared considering their architecture, support for metadata, existing programming interfaces, as well as their search mechanisms and community acceptance. In this process, the stakeholders' requirements are also taken into account. The results show that there is still plenty of room for improvement, mainly regarding the specificity of data descriptions in different domains, as well as the potential for integration of the data management platforms with existing research management tools. Nevertheless, depending on the context, some platforms can meet all or part of the stakeholders' requirements.

1 Introduction

The number of published scholarly papers is steadily increasing, and there is a growing awareness of the importance, diversity and complexity of data generated in research contexts [25]. The management of these assets is currently a concern for both researchers and institutions who have to streamline scholarly communication, while keeping record of research contributions and ensuring the correct framing of their contents [23, 18]. At the same time, academic institutions have new mandates, requiring data management activities to be carried out during the research projects, as a part of research grant contracts [14, 26]. These activities are inevitably supported by software platforms, increasing the demand for such infrastructures.

This paper presents an overview of several prominent research data management platforms that can be put in place by an institution to support part of its research data management workflow. It starts by identifying a set of well known repositories that are currently being used for either publications or data man-

Access File +
Edit File +
Contact Owner Share

File Metrics
0 Downloads

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Unpublished Dataset Private URL

Use a Private URL to allow those without Dataverse accounts to access your unpublished dataset. For more information about the Private URL feature, please refer to the User Guide.

This Private URL provides full read access to the dataset

<https://c8204ba4-c5d5-42c4-af03-272aa550e1e1-fr-by-cloud-instance.org/privateurl.xhtml?token=e9d5e78-a4dc-485e-b583-36868c907e3a>

Copy to Clipboard Disable Private URL Close

Private URL can be used by person, who has no account in Dataverse Link is valid until owner deletes it.

Preview available only for the most common formats

Dataverse overview (continue)

The screenshot shows the Dataverse_YL overview page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the NFDI4@t logo, a search bar, and links for User Guide, Support, and the user's name (Yulia Dikova). Below the navigation bar, a yellow banner displays a welcome message: "Welcome to NFDI4Cat repository prototype!". The main content area is titled "Dataverse_YL" and includes an "Unpublished" status indicator. A breadcrumb trail shows the path: "NFDI4Cat collections > test-dataverse > test-dataverse-subdataverse > Dataverse_YL > Pdf_test >". Below this, there is a section for "Users/Groups" with a sub-header "All the users and groups that have access to your dataverse." and a button "Assign Roles to Users/Groups". A table lists two users:

User/Group Name (Affiliation)	ID	Role	Action
Yulia Dikova	@Yulia.dikova	Contributor	Remove Assigned Role
Yulia Dikova	@Yulia.dikova	Admin	Role assigned at Dataverse_YL

Below the table, there is a section for "Roles" with a sub-header "All the roles set up in your dataverse, that you can assign to users and groups." and a list of roles with their descriptions and associated permissions:

- Admin** - A person who has all permissions for dataverses, datasets, and files, including approving requests for restricted data. Permissions: AddDataverse, AddDataset, ViewUnpublishedDataverse, ViewUnpublishedDataset, DownloadFile, EditDataverse, EditDataset, ManageDataversePermissions, ManageDatasetPermissions, ManageFilePermissions, PublishDataverse, PublishDataset, DeleteDataverse, DeleteDatasetDraft.
- Contributor** - For datasets, a person who can edit License + Terms, and then submit them for review. Permissions: ViewUnpublishedDataset, DownloadFile, EditDataset, DeleteDatasetDraft.
- Curator** - For datasets, a person who can edit License + Terms, edit Permissions, and publish datasets. Permissions: AddDataverse, AddDataset, ViewUnpublishedDataverse, ViewUnpublishedDataset, DownloadFile, EditDataset, ManageDatasetPermissions, ManageFilePermissions, PublishDataset, DeleteDatasetDraft.
- File Downloader** - A person who can download a published file. Permissions: DownloadFile.
- Member** - A person who can view both unpublished dataverses and datasets. Permissions: ViewUnpublishedDataverse, ViewUnpublishedDataset, DownloadFile.

The screenshot shows the "Assign Role" dialog box. The title is "Assign Role" and the subtitle is "Grant permissions to users and groups by assigning them a role." Below the subtitle, there is a section for "Users/Groups" with a text input field labeled "Enter User/Group Name". To the right of this field, there is a button "Assign Roles to Users/Groups". Below the "Users/Groups" section, there is a section for "Role" with a list of roles: Admin, Contributor, Curator, File Downloader, and Member. To the right of this list, there is a text box labeled "These are the permissions associated with the selected role." At the bottom of the dialog, there are two buttons: "Save Changes" and "Cancel".

It is possible to assign different roles to work with different data or datasets

Dataverse overview (continue)

Welcome to NFDI4Cat repository prototype!

NFDI4Cat collections >

Account - NFDI4Cat collections

My Data | Notifications | Account information | API Token

Notification settings

- test1 was created in Dataverse_YL. To learn more about what you can do with a dataset, check out the User Guide. Mar 17, 2023, 1:52:53 PM CET
- scrip1_test was created in Dataverse_YL. To learn more about what you can do with a dataset, check out the User Guide. Jan 30, 2023, 1:02:12 PM CET
- Picture_test was published in test-dataverse-subdataverse. Dec 12, 2022, 1:41:18 PM CET
- You have been granted the Admin role for test-dataverse-subdataverse. Dec 12, 2022, 1:41:16 PM CET
- Picture_test was created in test-dataverse-subdataverse. To learn more about what you can do with a dataset, check out the User Guide. Dec 12, 2022, 1:35:02 PM CET
- Doc_test was created in test-dataverse-subdataverse. To learn more about what you can do with a dataset, check out the User Guide. Dec 12, 2022, 1:19:44 PM CET
- Pdf_test was created in Dataverse_YL. To learn more about what you can do with a dataset, check out the User Guide. Dec 12, 2022, 1:08:59 PM CET
- Dataset New_Test1 has one or more tabular files that completed the tabular ingest process and are available in archival formats. Dec 7, 2022, 11:59:19 AM CET
- New_Test1 was created in Dataverse_YL. To learn more about what you can do with a dataset, check out the User Guide. Dec 7, 2022, 11:59:16 AM CET
- Dataverse_YL was created in test-dataverse-subdataverse. To learn more about what you can do with your dataverse, check out the User Guide. Dec 7, 2022, 11:58:42 AM CET
- You have been granted the Admin role for test-dataverse-subdataverse. Dec 2, 2022, 3:09:45 PM CET
- Welcome to NFDI4Cat collections! Get started by adding or finding data. Have questions? Check out the User Guide. Want to test out Dataverse features? Use our Demo Site. Also, check for your welcome email to verify your address. Dec 1, 2022, 3:22:20 PM CET

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Notification for users activity

NFDI4Cat collections > test-dataverse > test-dataverse-subdataverse > Dataverse_YL > New_Test1 >

Info – This draft version needs to be published. When ready for sharing, please go to the dataset page to publish it so that others can see these changes.

test4-more-lines.tab

This file is part of "New_Test1".

File Citation
Dikova, Yulia, 2022, "New_Test1", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1026>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION, test4-more-lines.tab [fileName], UNF:6:yrLAVv65MCDRQdDwmiRVw== [fileUNF]

Dataset Citation
Dikova, Yulia, 2022, "New_Test1", <https://doi.org/10.82013/NFDI4Cat-proto-bwc-1026>, NFDI4Cat collections, DRAFT VERSION, UNF:6:4OpRxJNR3/d+JMa2wXDUdQ== [fileUNF]

	найменування товару	одиниця виміру	ціна за 1 одиницю, грн	D	E	F	Номер чека	Постачальник
1	Туалетний папір Обухів, 60 м	рулок	7				1.0	Listex
2	Болога серветка Arieli, 80 шт.	упаковка	150				2.0	TOP Pack
3	Шампунь для волосся Dove 250 ml	штучка	80				3.0	Listex
4	Мило Dove, 125 gr	штучка	35				4.0	Listex
5	Антиперспірант Rexona, 100 ml	штучка	60				5.0	Listex
6	Ватний диск Sunny, 250 шт.	упаковка	20				6.0	Listex
7	Пральний порошок Ariel, 24 капс.	упаковка	100				7.0	Listex
8	Ополіскувач Silan 800 ml	штучка	80				8.0	KosmoSweet
9	Зубна паста Colgate Fresh 100 ml	штучка	35				9.0	Eva
10	Зубна щітка Oral-B	штучка	35				10.0	Eva
11							11.0	Eva
12	Постачальник						12.0	Eva
13	Thekangooro						13.0	Thekangooro
14	TOP Pack						14.0	Thekangooro
15	KosmoSweet						15.0	Thekangooro
16	Listex						16.0	Thekangooro
17	Eva						17.0	Thekangooro
18							18.0	TOP Pack
19							19.0	TOP Pack
20							20.0	TOP Pack
21	найменування товару	одиниця виміру	ціна за 1 одиницю, грн					
22	Туалетний папір Обухів, 60 м	рулок	7					
23	Болога серветка Arieli, 80 шт.	упаковка	150					
24	Шампунь для волосся Dove 250 ml	штучка	80					
25	Мило Dove, 125 gr	штучка	35					

Preview is possible only for most common formats. For other some additional extension are needed

CKAN overview

Organization - folder
Dataset - data or dataset

each group can includes organization, but additional extensions are needed

CKAN overview (continue)

The screenshot shows the 'Create Dataset' form in CKAN. The form is divided into two steps: '1 Create dataset' and '2 Add data'. The 'Create dataset' step includes fields for Title, Description, Tags, License, Organization, and Visibility. The 'Add data' step includes fields for Source, Version, Author, Author Email, Maintainer, Maintainer Email, and three Custom Field entries. A 'Next: Add Data' button is visible at the bottom right.

The screenshot shows the 'Add New Resource' form in CKAN. The form is divided into two steps: '1 Create dataset' and '2 Add data'. The 'Add data' step includes fields for Name, Description, and Format. There are 'Upload' and 'Link' buttons for the Data field. A 'Finish' button is visible at the bottom right.

The screenshot shows the 'Add New Resource' form in CKAN. The form is divided into two steps: '1 Create dataset' and '2 Add data'. The 'Add data' step includes fields for Name, Description, and Format. There are 'Upload' and 'Link' buttons for the Data field. A 'Finish' button is visible at the bottom right.

When adding a new dataset, a fairly small amount of metadata is specified. If necessary, the user can add any number of metadata fields as custom fields

user can upload data or put link

CKAN overview (continue)

It is possible to see users activity

For most common formats there is preview of data

DSpace overview

DSpace 7

DSpace is the world leading open source repository platform that enables organisations to:

- easily ingest documents, audio, video, datasets and their corresponding Dublin Core metadata
- open up this content to local and global audiences, thanks to the OAI-PMH interface and Google Scholar optimizations
- issue permanent urls and trustworthy identifiers, including optional integrations with handle.net and DataCite DOI

Join an international community of leading institutions using DSpace.

The test user accounts below have their password set to the name of this software in lowercase.

- Demo Site Administrator = dspacedemo+admin@gmail.com
- Demo Community Administrator = dspacedemo+commadmin@gmail.com
- Demo Collection Administrator = dspacedemo+colladmin@gmail.com
- Demo Submitter = dspacedemo+submit@gmail.com

Search the repository...

Communities in DSpace

Select a community to browse its collections.

Now showing 1 - 2 of 2

HLRS

NFDI

Home - Edit Submission

Drop files to attach them to the item, or browse

Collection Com1

Describe

Author

Author

Enter the author's name (family name, given name).

+ Add more

Title *

Title

Enter the main title of the item.

Other Titles

Other Titles

If the item has any alternative titles, please enter them here.

+ Add more

Date of Issue *

year month day

Publisher

Publisher

Enter the name of the publisher of the previously issued instance of this item.

Please give the date of previous publication or public distribution. You can leave out the day and/or month if they aren't applicable.

Citation

Citation

Enter the standard citation for the previously issued instance of this item.

Series/Report No.

Series Report No.

Enter the series and number assigned to this item by your community.

+ Add more

Identifiers

Discard

Save Save for Later Deposit

- Interface, upload
- Different possibilities for users
- Only main admin can create collections
- “Workflow” - admins of the collection must approve every publication - similar working process as in a library -> usage as Institutional Repository

DSpace overview (continue)

Sidebar for user

Sidebar for main admin

Only main admin can create community and collections. Then according access rights, user can work with them

ID	Name	Action
bb8f8331-0c86-4cd0-beef-a72ca95789e9	dspace admin	Select
52ecbe02-ed59-4c39-8a39-9029f0e31113	nadiia huskova	Select
b316f624-c4c0-451e-9f5c-a9b021e1221d	Preston Rodrigues	Select
3ab51fc6-0f75-4779-aeb2-656f6447efc0	taras petrenko	Select
2402bc17-15d2-44bf-9406-24ed6635e106	user1 user1	Select

Admin can manage role of user

DSpace overview (continue)

Only after checking the downloads and confirming them, the items appear in the community where they were supposed to be saved

Workflow tasks
Now showing 1 - 4 of 4

Filters

- Status: +
- Type: +
- Date: +
- Submitter: +

Settings

- Sort By: Most Relevant
- Results per page: 10

Item 1: New_test
(2023-03-19) Dikova Y.L.
No Abstract
Submitter: yuliia dikova
[Approve] [Reject] [Edit] [Return to pool]

Item 2: Picture test
(2023-02-20) Alex Bind
No Abstract
Submitter: yuliia dikova
[Approve] [Reject] [Edit] [Return to pool]

Item 3: PNG_test_role
(2023-01-15) Manal Talab
No Abstract
Submitter: yuliia dikova
[Approve] [Reject] [Edit] [Return to pool]

Item 4: 123
(2022-12-12) Ivan P.
No Abstract
Submitter: yuliia dikova
[Approve] [Reject] [Edit] [Return to pool]

Communities & Collections Statistics All of DSpace

Home • HLRS • My_collection

My_collection

Permanent URI for this collection <http://192.52.44.119:4000/handle/123456789/2>

Browse

- Recent Submissions
- By Issue Date
- By Author
- By Title
- By Subject

Now showing 1 - 5 of 21

- Item** PNG_test_role (2023-01-15) Manal Talab
- Item** Picture test (2023-02-20) Alex Bind
- Item** New_test (2023-03-19) Dikova Y.L.
- Item** Links for CKAN (2023-03-15) Dikova Y.L.
- Item** some file (2023-01-14) MP txt file

« 1 2 3 4 5 »

Tutorials

Simple item page

dc.contributor.author Someone + test

dc.date.accessioned 2022-06-03T11:59:00Z

dc.date.available 2022-06-03T11:59:00Z

dc.date.issued 2022-06-01

dc.identifier.uri <http://192.52.44.119:4000/handle/123456789/7>

dc.title Tutorials

Files

Original bundle

Now showing 1 - 1 of 1

No Thumbnail Available	Name: dSPACE_tutorial.pdf	Size: 2.28 MB	Format: Adobe Portable Document Format	Description:	Download
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License bundle

Now showing 1 - 1 of 1

No Thumbnail Available	Name: license.txt	Size: 1.71 KB	Format: Item-specific license agreed to upon submission	Description:	Download
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Collections

My_collection

DSpace does not provide a preview option. only download available

Analysis of user stories

Total amount of US - 60 (521 points)

- High - 49
- Middle - 10
- Low - 1

Priority (points)

- High 10
- Middle 3
- Low 1

Requirement can be...

- 1 = fulfilled,
- 0,5 = partially fulfilled,
- 0 = not fulfilled

Priority	DSpace	Dataverse	CKAN	InvenioRDM
High	40	43	39	40
middle	7	6	7	5
low	1	1	1	1
High	8	3	9	6
middle	1	1	1	2
low	0	0	0	0
High	1	3	2	3
middle	2	3	2	3
low	0	0	0	0
Summ	463,5	465,5	458,5	449

	fully realizable
	partly realizable
	Non realizable

Additional requirements (from administrators)

	Priority	Dataverse	Result	Invenio	Result	CKAN	Result	DSpace	Result	Comments
Installation procedure	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1	10	1 - simple Installation, Guides available, active Community 0.5 - additional technical support needed 0 - no guides, difficult installation process
Tools for enhancing functionality not needed	10	0.5	5	1	10	0.5	5	0.5	5	0 - need a lot of additional extensions 0.5 - extensions needed partly 1 - without any additional extensions
Role Based access	10	1	10	0	0	0	0	0.5	5	0 - strict set of roles 0.5 - different roles 1 - different role for the same user
Private link to data/data sets	10	1	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0 - impossible share data/datasets with private link 1 - possible share data/datasets with private link
Support for metadata schemes	10	1	10	0.5	5	0.5	5	0.5	5	0 - there is no fields for primary metadata 0.5 - limited set of primary metadata 1 - flexible metadata schemes
Final evaluation administrative			45		25		20		25	

Common results

According user requirements Dataverse has the most points (465,5)

According administrative requirements Dataverse also has the most points (45)

Common result shows, that Dataverse (total points = 510,5) is the most suitable candidate for the central repository

Main problems

- It is not possible to cover 100% of requirements (user stories) - additional implementation will be needed
- Repositories do not provide an ability to export all or selected publications directly from the database. Scripts needed.
- Additional extensions required to ensure analytical, statistical and visualization capabilities
- Limited functionality with metadata (Linked Data usually is not supported)
- Repositories do not provide interfaces for working with SPARQL
- Previewers usually support only the most common data formats (image formats, pdf, csv, etc...) – for specific formats extensions are needed
- Complex implementation of communication between the central repository and existing local systems and software products – integrating the already available pilot systems of our partners with the central repository into the new created NFDI4Cat infrastructure will be the next challenge.

Thank you

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